

Supplementary material - Toulzac *et al.* 2022. Soda maker for field anesthesia as a step towards a non-lethal identification of wild bees and other flower visitors.

Table S2. Anesthesia duration for specimens exposed more than 60 seconds to the CO₂. ITD: Inter-tegular distance. Temp: Air Temperature.

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.0038	4,172	11	1	120	301	No
Hymenoptera	<i>Xylocopa violacea</i>	M	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0011	8,389	22	1	120	0	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Xylocopa violacea</i>	M	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0011	8,389	20	1	120	301	No
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0093	1,47	26	1	120	0	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Arabis procurrens</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0123	1,51	25	2	120	58	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Arabis procurrens</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0124	1,314	25	2	120	57	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	15/3/21	SP3.21.0032	4,083	14	1	120	201	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	15/3/21	SP3.21.0033	3,576	14	1	120	222	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	15/3/21	SP3.21.0034	3,9	14	1	120	220	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	15/3/21	SP3.21.0035	3,923	13	1	120	270	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	15/3/21	SP3.21.0036	3,996	12	1	120	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	24/3/21	SP3.21.0043	4,106	17	1	120	190	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia bicornis</i>	M	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0055	3,571	18	1	240	0	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0126	6,972	25	2	120	74	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0132	6,511	20	2	120	71	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Muscari neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0121	4,758	25	2	120	79	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Vinca major</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0133	4,833	20	2	120	63	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Vinca major</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0137	6,426	20	2	120	76	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0139	6,197	16	2	120	81	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Vinca major</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0106	3,87	25	1	300	0	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0102	5,356	21	1	600	0	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0084	5,419	18	1	900	0	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Glechoma hederacea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0113	3,287	24	2	120	160	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0136	4,763	20	2	120	0	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0006	3,126	16	1	120	0	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0006	3,126	16	1	120	0	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Capture opportuniste</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0018	3,01	20	1	600	0	Yes
Diptera	Syrphidae		<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0052	3,907	22	1	600	180	No
Diptera	<i>Volucella sp.</i>		<i>Capture opportuniste</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0013	6,851	14	1	300	0	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Ficaria verna</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0129	2,246	25	2	120	61	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Erica carnea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0076	2,519	16	1	1800	0	Yes